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Mass Death, Population Decline, and Deprivation: A Capability Approach

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ABSTRACT

Genocide and mass violence research is predominantly focused on asymmetric, large-scale, deliberately targeted physical violence over relatively short timespans and involving stable perpetrator and victim groups. Recent attempts, such as Dirk Moses's, to redefine the field in order to be more inclusive of politically targeted groups, persecuted over longer time-spans within and across states go in the right direction but still fall short I argue. Instead, I propose a capability-based approach, following Amartya Sen, that enables consideration of a far broader range of violence's consequences such as starvation, systemic malnutrition, excess mortality from disease, and economic deprivation. After outlining the capability approach, I apply it to two case studies: (1) patterns of depopulation under (asymmetric) colonial violence that deprived indigenous communities of the capability to sustain their populations through violence, disease, and famines, a case which is already being scrutinized by genocide researchers; (2) sustained and much less asymmetric violence in the Central African Republic with high mortality, malnutrition, and economic deprivation. In both cases, the toll of physical violence is substantial, but violence's indirect consequences are far more lethal. I argue, that if we are to take seriously victims' suffering and loss of lives – a concern that ultimately normatively underwrites atrocity and conflict research – only the capability approach can encompass these cases.

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Introduction, or the Norms of Mass Death Accounting

“What is the experiential difference between a victim of genocide and a victim of collateral damage?”¹ Dirk Moses asks to cast a critical light on the genocide concept and the hierarchization of violence it entails whereby genocide is the crime of crimes and other forms of mass killings are somehow lesser crimes.² Moses asserts “[b]oth are innocent.”³

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¹ A. Dirk Moses, *The Problems of Genocide: Permanent Security and the Language of Transgression* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2021), 43.

² *Ibid.*, 472.

³ *Ibid.*, 43.

Therefore, genocide scholars who share Moses's ethical commitments need to look beyond the normative bounds of genocidal violence and consider broader forms of mass violence to prevent large-scale deaths. He contends that beyond genocide we also "need to consider noninternational armed conflicts, whether civil wars, internal repressions, or internal upheavals associated with forced development like the Chinese Great Leap Forward that cost the lives of twenty to thirty million people."⁴

The Great Leap famine (1958–62) is the biggest man-made population disaster event of the twentieth century in absolute numbers, quite likely in history (forty-five million dead according to Dikötter's most recent and substantial account of the famine), and the desire to include it in accounts of mass killings is understandable.⁵ Its scale and perhaps also a normative unease over its possible exclusion has given it a vibrant life, as it were, on the margins of atrocity scholarship despite never having entered into the genocide annals as a case of intentional killing. Snyder's *Bloodlands* mentions it, Kiernan's *Blood and Soil* treats it at equivalent length as genocides in the book, and Rummel specifically revised his data on "Democides" to include it.⁶ Even though Valentino concedes "there is no evidence to suggest that Mao or other Chinese leaders deliberately engineered the famine"⁷ (an assessment that still holds in Dikötter's account), he includes it in his book and dataset on mass killings.⁸ Similarly, a chapter in *The Historiography of Genocide* answers its titular question "Mao's China: The Worst Non-Genocidal Regime?" by asserting, under inclusion of the famine figures, that "Mao Zedong – in absolute figures – [is] a bigger mass murderer than Hitler or Stalin," despite conceding that intentional killing and forced suicides under Mao amounted to 4.5 to 9 million.⁹ To exclude the famine and its victims because of narrow definitional frameworks seems a shortcoming in any implicit or explicit normative judgments underwriting one's theoretical approach – or so the famine's vibrant life in the margins of genocide literature seems to suggest.

The famine figures, however, pose a problem for notions of targeted, intended killings – the domain of atrocity and conflict scholarship. For example, the Targeted Mass Killing dataset only includes the 2.5 million deliberate victims of destruction during the famine recorded by Dikötter and not the numbers of those who starved because they had not been *targeted* for death.¹⁰ For any quantitative assessment of mass killings and their correlates, this is a sound methodological choice. Yet, such exclusion stems ultimately from a

⁴ Ibid., 37.

⁵ Frank Dikötter, *Mao's Great Famine: The History of China's Most Devastating Catastrophe, 1958–62* (London: Bloomsbury, 2017), 324–34.

⁶ Timothy Snyder, *Bloodlands: Europe Between Hitler and Stalin*, 2nd ed. (New York: Basic Books, 2022), 524 n. 7; Ben Kiernan, *Blood and Soil: A World History of Genocide and Extermination from Sparta to Darfur* (New Haven, CT: Yale University Press, 2009), 512–38. See the note on Rummel's website: "DEATH BY GOVERNMENT: GENOCIDE AND MASS MURDER," <https://www.hawaii.edu/powerkills/NOTE1.HTM> (accessed 14 July 2023). Rudolph J. Rummel, *Death by Government*, 7th ed. (New Brunswick: Transaction, 2009), 36–42 ("democide").

⁷ Benjamin Valentino, *Final Solutions: Mass Killing and Genocide in the 20th Century* (Ithaca, NY: Cornell University Press, 2004), 126.

⁸ Jay Ulfelder and Benjamin Valentino, "Assessing Risks of State-Sponsored Mass Killing" (working paper, Political Instability Task Force, Washington, DC, 2008).

⁹ Jean-Louis Margolin, "Mao's China: The Worst Non-Genocidal Regime?" in *The Historiography of Genocide*, ed. Dan Stone (London: Palgrave Macmillan, 2008), 438 (quote), 455.

¹⁰ Charles Butcher et al., "Introducing the Targeted Mass Killing Data Set for the Study and Forecasting of Mass Atrocities," *Journal of Conflict Resolution* 64, nos. 7–8 (2020): 1524–47.

privileging of targeted killing as the locus of investigation – a choice that is a normative one well before it becomes a methodological and classificatory one. Naturally, any prioritization of targeted killings or mass atrocities over other forms of violence, including war, can itself draw on normative categories of “innocent victims” and substantially greater numbers of victims compared to military casualties.¹¹

Investigating the norms underpinning the destruction thresholds at which “the conscience of mankind” is shocked (e.g. genocide) as opposed to other forms of mass death that fall beneath such thresholds, therefore, is urgently called for.¹² Yet, while Moses is among those leading this call, he also focuses dominantly on direct violence. His more encompassing approach that calls for investigating all regimes that declare certain groups a security risk and thus aim to kill them for purposes of achieving “permanent security” is unlikely to accommodate the Great Leap famine.¹³ However, following in Moses’s footsteps, we may question, why should we privilege the death of a victim of atrocity – or “permanent security” – over that of someone ultimately dying of systemically high man-made mortality rates in a population?

Indeed, we should interrogate whether our current perpetrator-centric approach to violence that focuses on violence as resulting in *some form* from intentional, motivated, or deliberated actions – whether as genocide with specific intent, as an atrocity, or simply as a accepted foreseeable consequence of directed acts of killing (e.g. “collateral damage”) during conflict – is itself not normatively narrow. Both atrocity and, more specifically, genocide research focus on targeted, asymmetric, direct violence (with differently defined forms of intention), whereas the more general field of conflict research tends to focus on direct violence with *relatively* less particular emphasis on symmetry or targeting. My critique below applies especially to atrocity and genocide research (henceforth I will use atrocity to also denote genocide). Yet, insofar as it predominantly concerns itself with direct violence, rather than broader conflict-related mortality, many of my points here are relevant for conflict research as well. A victim-centered approach would be much more agnostic about intent or particular forms of suffering and focus on the reduction in the victim’s quality of life. Indeed, if atrocity and conflict scholarship is motivated by an ethics of understanding and preventing human death and suffering in the context of *large-scale death*, then it is ethically imperative to take a *victim-based approach* rather than a *perpetrator-based type of violent action approach*. Such an approach, which I below call the capability approach, could accommodate even – relatively – unintended but (almost) entirely man-made catastrophes, such as the Great Leap famine. Yet, the capability approach also accommodates other forms of extreme mortality that are less spectacular but ultimately more lethal. Sen and Drèze report that at 3.9 million excess deaths from disease and malnutrition in India compared to Mao’s China “India seems to manage to fill its cupboard with more skeletons every eight years than China put there in its years of shame [during Mao’s famine].”¹⁴ Furthermore, the spectacular

¹¹ Charles H. Anderton and Jurgen Brauer, “Datasets and Trends of Genocides, Mass Killings, and Other Civilian Atrocities,” in *Economic Aspects of Genocides, Other Mass Atrocities, and Their Preventions*, ed. Charles H. Anderton and Jurgen Brauer (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2016), 65–7. Since 1900, state-perpetrated atrocities have killed 2.7 times more than interstate wars. Despite receiving intense attention, forty-three years of terrorism were merely as lethal as a month of the Rwandan genocide.

¹² Moses, *Problems of Genocide*, 4.

¹³ Only two pages mention the famine: *Ibid.*, 27, 37.

¹⁴ Jean Drèze and Amartya Sen, *Hunger and Public Action* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1989), 204–25, (quote) 215.

catastrophe of Mao's famine blinds atrocity scholars to India's slow-creeping death by malnutrition, but also to the unprecedented improvements in life expectancy under Mao. "Between 1950 and 1980, China experienced the most rapid sustained increase in life expectancy of any population in documented global history" that was largely the result of sustained public health programmes and education (notwithstanding the sharp mortality reversal during the famine).¹⁵

Of course, driven to its ultimate conclusion, this perspective does not exclude natural disasters (e.g. earthquakes) and disease-based suffering. At this point, we seem to have firmly departed from the staked-out terrain of atrocity studies and entered the fields of disaster response and epidemiology. There is, indeed, much merit in taking a more expansive view of mortality and life expectancy that demography, epidemiology, and social medicine afford. We can learn much about a society's underlying norms that lead it to direct its socio-economic and political capabilities to different groups with differing degrees of priority to fight, say, diseases – humankind's greatest killers. While these fields widely draw on analyses of such social capabilities to explain different responses to, say, disease mortality, serious consideration of how capabilities and deprivation thereof interlink with violence are yet to receive appropriate attention in atrocity scholarship. I seek to begin rectifying this gap.

In the following, I outline this "capability approach" by, first, discussing its origins in the research of Amartya Sen. Second, I discuss its implications for atrocity research and show that it integrates with and takes further recent trajectories in the field. Third, I examine a case of atrocity-related research where the capability approach has been implicitly applied. This is the case of high mortality, epidemics, and depopulation during the expansion and reign of modern European empires. Of course, with so vast a topic I can only give a rough sketch of core findings and implications, and my main imperative here is to bring the different strands of existing research together under the explicit umbrella of the capability approach. Fourth, I examine a detailed present-day case study of interlocking patterns of violence, deprivation, disease, and food insecurity in the Central African Republic, a region that itself looks back on major historical episodes of mortality and population decline during the nineteenth-century slave trade. In conclusion, I discuss the limitations and broader implications of the capability approach for atrocity and conflict research.

Capability as Approach to Human-Caused Mass Death

Violence against a person deprives that person of capabilities. The most basic capability is that to survive. Killing deprives one of this capability. There are many other ways of being deprived of this capability. Death by disease or malnutrition are common ways. The

¹⁵ Kimberly Babiarz et al., "An Exploration of China's Mortality Decline under Mao: A Provincial Analysis, 1950–80," *Population Studies* 69, no. 1 (2015): 39. Neither Hitler nor Stalin could make such claims for the populations they controlled. Stalin's collectivization campaigns caused massive life expectancy decreases in particularly Soviet Russia and Ukraine (no data exist on severely affected Kazakhstan) that were only regained in late 1930 (only to immediately plummet with the onset of WWII). In Stalin's final years life expectancy increased somewhat. The Nazi-caused WWII resulted in a substantial pan-European life expectancy decline by about 10 years. Given Nazi plans to deport (expecting death) or to kill outright approximately eighty per cent of Eastern European populations, little speculation is needed as to the Nazi's effect on European life expectancy had they won. Life expectancies: Johan Mackenbach, "Political Conditions and Life Expectancy in Europe, 1900–2008," *Social Science & Medicine* 82 (2013): 134–46. Nazi plans: Christian Ingrao, *The Promise of the East: Nazi Hopes and Genocide, 1939–43*, trans. Andrew Brown (Newark: Polity, 2019).

factors depriving someone of the capability to survive starvation can be very complex, even in seemingly simple cases of death during famine. Famine, unless in the more famous man-made cases of Mao's Great Leap or Stalin's 1932–33 collectivization famine, was long assumed to be a case of "natural" occurrence carrying off thousands or millions, and states idly had to stand by because they simply lacked sufficient food-stuffs to distribute to the starving. History is full of leaders bemoaning Malthusian conundrums posed by exploding populations and lagging food production leading to inevitable famines.¹⁶ In the 1980s, however, Sen showed that the distribution of foodstuffs mattered more than total food availability. Famines often happen in cases of entitlement deprivation in which the famished have insufficient capabilities to access food, for example when in the Bengal famine food prices rose above agricultural labourers' capability to exchange labour or valuables for sufficient food and socio-political responses (that are capabilities) were inadequate to make up for this deprivation.¹⁷ Ultimately, the deaths of the Bengal famine were thus the result of a set of predominantly human-caused deprivations. Sen's examination of famines predominantly focused on economic factors, but subsequent studies found that in the twentieth-century political factors, ranging from intentional infliction of starvation to negligence and conflict, were even more importantly involved in famines (twenty-one out of thirty-two recorded famines) and accounted for eighty-eight to ninety-three per cent of the total estimated 70.1–80.4 million famine deaths.¹⁸

Sen and others expanded this thinking beyond the study of malnutrition and famines and developed the "capability approach." Capabilities are one's real opportunities or freedoms to convert a set of goods into a life one values. Different individuals may not be able to convert the same set of goods into the same capabilities – disabled and able-bodied persons may derive different capabilities from an identical income.¹⁹ Sen gives general examples of capabilities in relation to political, economic, and social freedoms.²⁰ Capabilities should be considered as interacting with each other in bundles. Some bundles, such as access to nutrition and healthcare that facilitate the most basic capability to survive, are particularly important. Economists may focus on economic capabilities in terms of GDP, yet such a totalized aggregate insufficiently captures even the very basic capabilities of a population's long-term survival, as in the case of high-growth but low-life-expectancy Brazil at the time of Sen's writing. In turn, vast improvements in basic capabilities to survive are not necessarily pre-conditioned on high economic growth, as can be seen by the case of Mao's China (when one's investigative scope isn't limited to his famine).²¹ The capability approach demands that, firstly, we explicitly reflect on the *normative assumptions* underpinning our valuation of capabilities, and that we consider the implications of various capability bundles *holistically*, over varied time-spans, geographies, and collectives of peoples.

¹⁶ Alex De Waal, *Mass Starvation: The History and Future of Famine* (Cambridge: Polity, 2018), 36–52.

¹⁷ Amartya Sen, *Poverty and Famines: An Essay on Entitlement and Deprivation* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1981), 45–51 (entitlement), 52–86 (Bengal famine).

¹⁸ Stephen Devereux, "Famine in the Twentieth Century," *IDS Working Papers* 105 (2000): 6; see also: De Waal, *Mass Starvation*.

¹⁹ Amartya Sen, *Development as Freedom* (New York: Knopf, 1999), 88.

²⁰ *Ibid.*, 38–40.

²¹ *Ibid.*, 45.

There is some debate as to which capabilities should be endorsed as the normative centre of consideration. Sen largely refrains from producing an “‘aggregate’ measure of deprivation” or endorsing one particular capability bundle, despite predominantly discussing mortality, undernourishment, and illiteracy,²² whereas Nussbaum creates an explicit list.²³ My predominant concern here is with what I consider to be the most basic: the capability to live a full and healthy lifespan. In the context of violence-related mortality, therefore, my focus is on the deprivation of this most basic capability. Despite Sen’s hesitation to espouse a particular set of capabilities as normative centre, mortality and life expectancy have been central to his deliberations and will also be in what follows.²⁴

While the capability approach is applicable to cases of deprivation unrelated to violence, my focus here is on the subset of capability deprivations in relation to atrocity and conflict where the approach considerably broadens our considerations of their causes and consequences. In order to demonstrate the benefit of using the capability approach, I consider two related concepts: human security and structural violence. Although human security similarly focuses on “downside risks” that “threaten human survival,” and unsurprisingly Sen was influentially involved in developing the concept,²⁵ its scope is limited to threats whereas the comprehensive ethical theory of the capability approach, for example, accommodates famine *and* life expectancy increases under Mao’s reign. Even if such positive developments are not a primary concern here due to our focus on large-scale mortality during atrocity and conflict, they are normatively relevant and a broader ethical theory that integrates down- and upturns is desirable and provided by the capability approach. The cases below were selected not only because of extreme mortality but also because they lacked fundamental capability improvements that would put the focused-on extreme deprivations into relief.

I am deeply sympathetic to the occasional attempts within atrocity research to broaden and reframe atrocity within structural violence frameworks. However, these still tend to focus on various notions of intentional targeting and asymmetry (e.g. colonial or state-orchestrated violence or the global North–South axis).²⁶ Intent and asymmetry are valid subjects of research into causes (that the capability lens still allows us to pursue), but the capability approach is not constrained by requiring either. Since the structural violence concept describes any deprivation as some form of violence, all deprivation, by virtue of being violence, thus falls within the remit of its research from the outset.²⁷ Further, using violence as a universal descriptor misleadingly suggests violence as an underlying universal explanatory framework for what can be very disparate forms of deprivation.²⁸ Instead, I suggest, that using a capability lens within the context of atrocity and conflict broadens our analysis beyond an exclusive focus on large-scale direct

²² *Ibid.*, 103.

²³ Martha Nussbaum, “Capabilities as Fundamental Entitlements: Sen and Social Justice,” *Feminist Economics* 9, nos. 2–3 (2003): 33–59.

²⁴ Sen, *Development as Freedom*, 35–53.

²⁵ Amartya Sen and Sadako Ogata, *Human Security Now* (New York: UN, 2003), 8.

²⁶ Adam Jones, “Genocide and Structural Violence: Charting the Terrain,” in *New Directions in Genocide Research*, ed. Adam Jones (New York: Routledge, 2012), 132–52; Nafeez Ahmed, “Structural Violence as a Form of Genocide. The Impact of the International Economic Order,” *Entelequia. Revista Interdisciplinar* (2007): 3–41.

²⁷ Johan Galtung, “Violence, Peace, and Peace Research,” *Journal of Peace Research* 6, no. 3 (1969): 167–91.

²⁸ Kenneth E. Boulding, “Twelve Friendly Quarrels with Johan Galtung,” *Journal of Peace Research* 14, no. 1 (1977): 81–4.

Figure 1 The fields of capability deprivation in a Venn diagram. The forms of severe deprivations this paper is most concerned with are excess mortality related to large-scale violence, large-scale violence deaths, and their interrelation.

violence toward those large-scale deprivations, particularly excess mortality, that are directly or more indirectly related to this violence. We can pursue these deprivations without also universalizing the notion of violence. Because all deprivations fall under the capability approach and deprivations are linked with each other, we can pursue, as desired, causes and forms of deprivation outward even beyond mortality (see [Figure 1](#)) while remaining within the same theoretical framework without assuming a global scope as a theoretical preset in the way the structural violence approach does. Even when the capability-based investigation into atrocity and conflict-related excess mortality is our main focus, its situatedness within the broader ethical scope of the capability approach not only ensures that we include conflicts and atrocities in our purview that are somehow “less” than genocide but also that our framework does not systemically blind us to less attention-grabbing violence-unrelated large-scale deprivations (e.g. malnutrition in India).

The capability approach demands thorough investigations into conflict-related excess mortality that are predominantly led outside of atrocity research in medical and demographic literature where they are also only relatively recent subjects of study.²⁹ Using a

²⁹ E.g. Bethany Lacina and Nils Gleditsch, “Monitoring Trends in Global Combat: A New Dataset of Battle Deaths,” *European Journal of Population* 21, no. 2 (2005): 145–66; Mohammed Jawad et al., “Estimating Indirect Mortality Impacts of Armed Conflict in Civilian Populations: Panel Regression Analyses of 193 Countries, 1990–2017,” *BMC Medicine* 18, no. 1 (2020): 266.

capability lens means that we adjust our normative framework to include these victims in our study of atrocity. The novelty of this perspective becomes apparent when we contrast it with, at some risk of generalizing, typical tendencies in atrocity research. Atrocity scholars are typically concerned with violence that is *asymmetric*, *explosive* (over a short period of time), *expansive* (concerning large numbers or proportions of people), *intensive* (involving severe harm, usually death), and *direct* and *intended causes* of harm (as opposed to more indirect forces depriving a group of, say, economic means to survive). While my perspective informed by the capability approach also focuses on *intensive* (predominantly death) and *expansive* (affecting many) violence and deprivation, the other forms play a lesser role in favour of a larger picture. Long-term and less expansive violence or deprivation may ultimately affect as many or more people than spectacularly explosive and expansive violence. Time-windows (shorter vs longer term) are not in themselves normatively relevant. Rather, lives lost to basic capability deprivation are the central concern. Similarly, while it may normatively matter to the victim to some extent whether they die from direct violence or more structural forces of deprivation, it arguably matters much less than most default perspectives of atrocity scholarship presume.

Below I briefly discuss how the capability approach can be advantageously integrated into already existing scholarly trends in the field. Then I examine a closer example of such a scholarly trend – depopulation and deprivation under colonialism – where capabilities already play a central role. I then scrutinize another, recent example – The Central African Republic – which has been effectively completely ignored by the scholarly atrocity lens but demands attention (as do other cases) from the perspective of capability deprivation.

Integration into Current Scholarship

The capability approach calls for consideration of much broader forms of deprivation, rather than the direct, explosive violence dominating atrocity (or also conflict) research. However, the capability approach integrates well into already existing trends in atrocity studies, as I briefly sketch now. Recent atrocity scholarship has questioned and reconsidered the spatialities and temporalities of genocide. Mark Levene focuses on “zone[s] of genocide” (e.g. Eastern Anatolia split across today’s Turkey and Iraq) over a much larger time-span (1878–1923 and beyond, rather than the 1915–16 dates given for the Armenian genocide) and including further victim groups than typically considered (i.e. Kurds, Pontic Greeks, Assyrians rather than only Armenians).³⁰ In the same vein, Donald Bloxham’s re-examines the Holocaust in the context and as a consequence of a broader European history of violence over preceding decades.³¹ René Lemarchand re-frames the violence of the 1994 Rwandan genocide within the broader geographical region of Central Africa (including Congo and Burundi) beyond the temporal confines of the iconic 100 days of the genocide.³² Christian Gerlach, in turn, emphasizes the multi-institutional involvements and the multiplicity and heterogeneity of groups

³⁰ Mark Levene, “Creating a Modern ‘Zone of Genocide’: The Impact of Nation- and State-Formation on Eastern Anatolia, 1878–1923,” *Holocaust and Genocide Studies* 12, no. 3 (1998): 393–433; see further: Benny Morris and Dror Ze’evi, *The Thirty-Year Genocide: Turkey’s Destruction of Its Christian Minorities, 1894–1924* (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 2019).

³¹ Donald Bloxham, *The Final Solution: A Genocide* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009).

³² René Lemarchand, *The Dynamics of Violence in Central Africa* (Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press, 2009).

participating in structurally concerted projects of mass killings. His approach is more inclusive of different victim groups and their different degrees of deprivation and emphasizes the multi-causal nature of different forms violence.³³ The shared trajectory of these innovations is a broadening of the causal and spatio-temporal horizons of violence and – at least somewhat – a more inclusive scrutiny of violence impacts that otherwise may fall below the threshold of genocide. They scope the spatio-temporal neighbourhoods of genocide for violence and deprivations that can serve as explanatory factors of genocide.

While quantitative scholars have been using more extensive definitions of atrocity and mass violence for decades and thus de facto substantially expanded the narrow legal or even historical frames of genocide,³⁴ their emphasis on quantitative methodological workability sidestepped rather than explicitly conceptually challenged the normativity of the genocide paradigm's political foundations. Nonetheless, quantitative atrocity scholarship has made the connection between atrocity and deprivation very measurably clear. Its models explicitly include capability deprivations, such as infant mortality,³⁵ GDP, GDP growth,³⁶ and political disenfranchisement and instability,³⁷ in the independent variables. At the same time, explicitly conceptual recent research highlights and questions the normative political underpinning of the UN Genocide Convention's creation that de-politicizes the genocide concept.³⁸ Moses, for instance, questions the timeframes of mass violence while also calling for an investigation into the political norms that mask our views of destruction. Pertinently, he calls for including in the study of mass atrocity strategic bombing campaigns, drone killings, and even less direct forms of death-dealing such as starvation through blockades, practiced not only by authoritarian regimes but also liberal democracies.³⁹ The capability approach takes this even further and examines, for example, malnutrition, starvation, and disease exposure in contexts of violence, rather than only when a group is deliberately targeted, as we will see in the case of the Central African Republic.

The capability approach also encompasses environmental destructions – common in lands of indigenous peoples – discussed in contemporary scholarship (especially in international criminal law) on the genocide-ecocide nexus and the unprecedented environmental destruction brought about by global extractivist capitalism, since land destruction is directly linked to capability deprivation of peoples.⁴⁰ Ecocide scholarship is already concerned with forms of capability deprivation beyond directly caused deaths and very explicitly considers structural factors like capitalist economics. Insofar

³³ Christian Gerlach, *Extremely Violent Societies: Mass Violence in the Twentieth-Century World* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2010).

³⁴ Barbara Harff and Ted Robert Gurr, "Toward Empirical Theory of Genocides and Politicides: Identification and Measurement of Cases Since 1945," *International Studies Quarterly* 32, no. 3 (1988): 359–71.

³⁵ Ulfelder and Valentino, "Assessing Risks of State-Sponsored Mass Killing."

³⁶ Gary Uzonyi et al., "Genocide, Politicide, and the Prospects of Democratization since 1900," *Journal of Conflict Resolution* 65, no. 9 (2021): 1521–50.

³⁷ Nam Kyu Kim, "Revolutionary Leaders and Mass Killing," *Journal of Conflict Resolution* 62, no. 2 (2018): 289–317.

³⁸ Moses, *Problems of Genocide*, 16–28; Amanda Alexander, "The Ethics of Violence: Recent Literature on the Creation of the Contemporary Regime of Law and War," *Journal of Genocide Research* 25, no. 2 (2023): 235–51; Benjamin Meiches, *The Politics of Annihilation: A Genealogy of Genocide* (Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 2019), 7.

³⁹ Moses, *Problems of Genocide*, (bombing) 1–7, (timeframe) 2, (blockades) 6, 166, 443–4.

⁴⁰ Martin Crook, Damien Short, and Nigel South, "Ecocide, Genocide, Capitalism and Colonialism: Consequences for Indigenous Peoples and Glocal Ecosystems Environments," *Theoretical Criminology* 22, no. 3 (2018): 298–317; Sailesh Mehta and Prisca Merz, "Ecocide – a New Crime against Peace?" *Environmental Law Review* 17, no. 1 (2015): 3–7; Damien Short, *Redefining Genocide: Settler Colonialism, Social Death and Ecocide* (London: Zed, 2016).

as its scope includes the capability deprivations wrought by long-term and global climate change, it reframes the typical spatio-temporal horizons of consideration. The capability approach can serve as the theoretical umbrella explicitly connecting the different strands of the ecocide-genocide nexus and climate change research to the human cost of climate change often framed in capability terms.⁴¹

Colonial Violence and Depopulation as Deprivation

A case, where scholarship has already done significant legwork towards a capability-based picture is historical research into mortality, depopulation, famines, diseases, and violence under colonialism. At some risk of generalizing different empires and historical periods, it seems uncontroversial to characterize colonial empires as mass deprivation regimes. According to a very recent assessment taking a capability view, capitalism in the European empires, especially in 1850–1950, led to a “decline in wages to below subsistence, a deterioration in human stature [height], and an upturn in premature mortality,” even if PPP-adjusted GDP per capita may have risen during that same period.⁴² Global-scale colonial food markets paired with food shortages in various colonized locales could elicit incredibly lethal famines with millions of deaths, because imperial centres with purchasing power politically and economically skewed in their favour could buy up foodstuff even from places where there was a dire undersupply.⁴³ Massive population declines between ten per cent (Uganda) and nineteen per cent (Congo) occurred under colonial regimes ruling much of Sub-Saharan Africa from 1890 to 1920.⁴⁴ Although statistics are somewhat unreliable, the worst case may have been German colonial Namibia (then German South West Africa) with a population decline of twenty-three to thirty-five per cent during the Herero and Nama genocide (1904–08),⁴⁵ topping even the staggering nineteen per cent population decline in Congo under Belgian king Leopold II.

Large-scale depopulation of indigenous peoples under colonialism also took place during the conquest of the Americas. While violence played a prominent role here, the biggest killers were germs and the explanation and description of these disease-related deaths resemble that of famine descriptions above. Akin to the Malthusian shoulder shrugging about famines, historical narratives about diseases often see infections and

⁴¹ See discussion of morbidity and mortality: Timothy Lenton et al., “Quantifying the Human Cost of Global Warming,” *Nature Sustainability* 6 (2023); Camilo Mora et al., “Global Risk of Deadly Heat,” *Nature Climate Change* 7, no. 7 (2017).

⁴² Dylan Sullivan and Jason Hinkel, “Capitalism and Extreme Poverty: A Global Analysis of Real Wages, Human Height, and Mortality since the Long 16th Century,” *World Development* 161 (2023): 4.

⁴³ Mike Davis, *Late Victorian Holocausts: El Niño Famines and the Making of the Third World* (London: Verso, 2002), see e.g. 31–2; Tim Dyson, *A Population History of India: From the First Modern People to the Present Day* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2018), 139–40.

⁴⁴ Sullivan and Hinkel, “Capitalism and Extreme Poverty,” 11.

⁴⁵ *Die Kämpfe der deutschen Truppen in Südwestafrika: Der Feldzug gegen die Hereros*, vol. 1 of *Großer Generalstab* (Berlin: Königliche Hofbuchhandlung, 1906), 9–10; Isabel V. Hull, *Absolute Destruction: Military Culture and the Practices of War in Imperial Germany* (Ithaca, NY: Cornell University Press, 2006), 7–8 n.2 (Herero population), 88 (death toll); Brian Mitchell, *International Historical Statistics: Africa, Asia and Oceania 1750–2010*, vol. 1 (London: Palgrave Macmillan, 2013), 17 (1921 census). Death estimates used here and by Hull are based on German 1911 census data Dietrich Baecker, “Kolonialstatistik und Bemerkungen dazu,” *Jahrbuch über die deutschen Kolonien* 4 (1911): 230. Percentage given in text above is based on my calculations with a pre-1904 Namibian population of 200,000, the commonly accepted pre-genocide Herero and Nama populations of respectively 80,000 and 20,000, and a genocidal death toll of 60,000 Herero and 10,000 Nama. Even assuming a much larger initial population of 300,000 (very unlikely given that a 1921 British census estimated Namibia’s inhabitants, including white settlers, at 229,000 people), the depopulation would be over twenty-three per cent.

outcomes as biologically overdetermined and inevitable – especially in cases of disenfranchised, precarious minorities – while ignoring the substantial socio-political and economic factors involved in disease transmission and mortality.⁴⁶ Recent research on colonial depopulation patterns in the Americas sharply questions such naturalizing narratives and instead points to the substantially increased risks of exposure to and mortality by diseases owing to the extreme disruptions of removals, flight, and violence throughout centuries of colonization by Europeans as major explanatory factors of the population decline. While genocides by European colonizers of native peoples in the Americas,⁴⁷ Africa (see note 45), and Oceania⁴⁸ did occur, direct violence-related deaths in most cases do not seem to account for the majority of the victims.⁴⁹ The research by medical historians and demographers casts the net more widely to consider what, at heart, are colonizer-imposed capability deprivations that are less noticeable than direct colonial violence but have ultimately had lethal consequences on a much larger scale. These capability deprivations, often occurring below direct-violence thresholds typically considered in atrocity research, are closely causally related to direct violence and thus complicate such categorical approaches to violence by pointing to a much more nuanced continuum of deprivations that is integral to the capability approach.

Studying the proto-historic period (1492–1659) in the south-eastern US, Kelton states ecological factors were more important drivers of mass deaths than the often stated genetic ones, even if genetic homogeneity may have played a role.⁵⁰ There is little evidence for extensively or intensely lethal epidemics and, instead, Kelton assesses that warfare and drought were likely bigger factors.⁵¹ Ostler, on the other hand, notes that after population declines owing to violent colonial onslaughts and territorial losses, entailing their being deprived of crucial food resources like hunting grounds and farmlands, many indigenous populations stabilized or were even recovering in the late seventeenth and early eighteenth centuries. Yet, then prevalent theories of the “vanishing Indian” sparked the mass removals of native peoples to reservations that led to enormous population declines from diseases and malnutrition (which

⁴⁶ A contemporary such naturalizing narrative: Jared Diamond, *Guns, Germs, and Steel: The Fates of Human Societies* (New York: Norton, 1999), 195–214, esp. 210–14. Further narratives across history: Jeffrey Ostler, *Surviving Genocide: Native Nations and the United States from the American Revolution to Bleeding Kansas* (New Haven, CT: Yale University Press, 2019), 2; Paul Kelton, *Epidemics and Enslavement: Biological Catastrophe in the Native Southeast, 1492–1715* (Lincoln: University of Nebraska Press, 2007), 47; David S. Jones, “Virgin Soils Revisited,” *William and Mary Quarterly* 60, no. 4 (2003): 714–15; Tony Barta, “Mr Darwin’s Shooters: On Natural Selection and the Naturalizing of Genocide,” *Patterns of Prejudice* 39, no. 2 (2005): 116–37; Enzo Traverso, *Moderne und Gewalt. Eine europäische Genealogie des Nazi-Terrors*, trans. Paul B. Kleiser (Köln: Neuer ISP, 2003), 57–67; Jones, “Virgin Soils Revisited,” 707–12; Tai Edwards and Paul Kelton, “Germs, Genocides, and America’s Indigenous Peoples,” *Journal of American History* 107, no. 1 (2020): 52–76.

⁴⁷ Benjamin Madley, *An American Genocide: The United States and the California Indian Catastrophe, 1846–1873* (New Haven, CT: Yale University Press, 2016). Ostler, *Surviving Genocide*, 383–7.

⁴⁸ A. Dirk Moses, “An Antipodean Genocide? The Origins of the Genocidal Moment in the Colonization of Australia,” *Journal of Genocide Research* 2, no. 1 (2000): 89–106; A. Dirk Moses, ed., *Genocide and Settler Society: Frontier Violence and Stolen Indigenous Children in Australian History* (New York: Berghahn, 2005); Rebe Taylor, “Genocide in Van Diemen’s Land (Tasmania), 1803–1871,” in *The Cambridge World History of Genocide: Genocide in the Indigenous, Early Modern and Imperial Worlds, from c.1535 to World War One*, ed. Ben Kiernan et al., vol. 2 (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2023), 481–507.

⁴⁹ Madley, *An American Genocide*, 1 (population estimate), 10 (depopulation), 12 (violent deaths). Madley’s account of perhaps the largest-scale genocidal episode in US history records that “non-Indians killed at least 9,492 to 16,094 California Indians, and probably more, between 1846 and 1873” out of a total population of 150,000. Madley’s upper bound of violent deaths (16,094) thus accounts for 13.4 per cent of the total 80 per cent population decline.

⁵⁰ Kelton, *Epidemics and Enslavement*, 45–6.

⁵¹ *Ibid.*, 95.

increases susceptibility to diseases).⁵² For example, the populations of the southern US, such as the Choctaws and Cherokees, in the late 1700s and early 1800s were rising.⁵³ Yet, the Choctaw cholera pandemic around 1832 took place because of US removal policies when Choctaws were transported on overcrowded and infected steamboats or exhausted themselves walking hundreds of miles to their reservations, while those Choctaw populations that escaped the removal policies by moving west fared significantly better despite the environmental and social stresses of leaving their lands.⁵⁴ Thus, whatever the actual or purported intention of US politicians and administrators in drafting the removal policies, colonial capability deprivation as a consequence of removal appears to be the most significant driver of mortality. Several of the most precipitous population declines of the Sauk and Mesquakie, Potawatomis, Ottawa, Kanza, Osage, and Ioways populations, among numerous others, were during the time of removal to reservations by their respective colonizing governments.⁵⁵ Smallpox was imported by the colonizers and is infamous for decimating indigenous populations. But given that there was some acquired immunity to smallpox among the Omahas and the Otoe-Missourias, its devastating impact during the 1831–32 epidemic is instead to be attributed to “severe social stress and material deprivation” that themselves were the result of “US expansion.”⁵⁶ For the Caribbean and Latin America, Livi-Bacci comes to very similar findings. While diseases were the main cause of depopulation, their incredible lethality was greatly amplified by the colonizer-caused deprivation of direct violence, enslavement, and dislocation. In the Caribbean, mass depopulation from violence and gold mining was well underway before the first diseases arrived, while forced-labor gold mining – drawing in up to a third of a subsistence-farming population now deprived of vital agricultural workers – and intra-Inca, Spanish-Inca, and then intra-Spanish wars in what is today’s Peru and Bolivia brought famine and increased susceptibility to diseases. Akin to those Choctaws that survived by escaping removal and the closest approximation we have to a South American treatment-control study, the Guaraní in today’s Paraguay were thriving under the Jesuits who provided basic healthcare and protected them from the worst conquistador deprivations.⁵⁷ Thus, adopting a lens exclusively focused on genocidal violence discounts such mortality and depopulation, despite their direct causal link to colonial impositions of capability deprivation and violence.

It has been commonplace knowledge for decades that socio-economic, political, and cultural capability deprivations are major determinants of the health of demographic groups. For instance, in 1993, Sen calculated that African-American male survival rates in Harlem, New York City, were worse than in Bangladesh, China, and the Indian state of Kerala.⁵⁸ Similarly, an assessment of contemporary “health disparities” between

⁵² Ostler, *Surviving Genocide*, 183–214.

⁵³ *Ibid.*, 188–9.

⁵⁴ *Ibid.*, 250–6; see also: Paul Kelton, “Pandemic Injustice: Irish Immigrant, Enslaved African American, and Choctaw Experiences with Cholera in 1832,” *Journal of Southern History* 88, no. 1 (2022): 98–110.

⁵⁵ Ostler, *Surviving Genocide*, 351–6.

⁵⁶ *Ibid.*, 241.

⁵⁷ Massimo Livi Bacci, *Conquest: The Destruction of the American Indians* (Cambridge: Polity, 2008), 89–118 (Caribbean), 65–88 (mining), 157–92 (Peru and Bolivia), 193–224 (Guaraní), 231–6 (summary).

⁵⁸ Sen, *Development as Freedom*, 23.

indigenous and non-indigenous Canadians concludes that they “are directly and indirectly associated with social, economic, cultural and political inequities.”⁵⁹ Yet, it has taken remarkably long for such a capability-focused approach to be applied in studies of depopulation and mortality during colonial regimes. And while the recent discussions of colonial genocides dispel the myth that colonial peoples “merely” died from disease (see notes 45, 47, 48), they cannot account for the much wider destruction wrought by colonial institutions whose systematic policies of capability deprivation, including but going beyond direct violence, are causally entwined with high mortality, precarity, and mass death. Beyond this research in historical social medicine, historical demography, and colonial genocides, we should also consider the causal entwinement of capability deprivations with mass death in more contemporary cases and acknowledge its critical importance in studies of direct and explosive violence.

Deprivation and Violence in the Central African Republic

We have seen how the capability approach encompasses the case of colonial violence. This case serves as the clearest yet for how the approach integrates into existing research on atrocity. Now, I examine the case of the contemporary Central African Republic (hereafter CAR) that has so far escaped the narrower frames of atrocity scholarship yet which from a capability lens urgently calls for consideration. While contemporary deprivations in CAR have their own particular dynamics that will be examined below, no discussion of CAR’s current fundamental level of deprivation can ignore CAR’s history. CAR similarly looks back on a history of depopulation and mass death during the pre-colonial slave raids and the concessionary economic exploitation under the French colonial reign inspired by Belgian king Leopold II’s Congo.⁶⁰ Especially the pre-colonial violent slave raids from sultanates in southern Chad and particularly Sudan led to large migrations of CAR ethnicities to the south, epidemics, famines, and, in combination with slavery, up to a possible loss of half the population (although data are very unreliable).⁶¹ Members of the Banda ethnicity stopped cultivating their lands altogether to prevent alerting slavers to their presence and, generally, many groups transitioned – with intermittent success and periods of starvation – to cultivating the less conspicuous cassava instead of other, traditional crops.⁶² The northeast, once CAR’s most populous part but also the closest ingress point to slaver aggression, became CAR’s most depopulated part that it is to this day.⁶³

Extreme deprivation and mortality, including but not reducible to mortality caused by periods of extensive direct violence, characterize CAR’s history for the last two centuries and last into the present with particular spikes of violence in the last two decades. Nevertheless, none of the three major genocide-centred journals (*Journal of Genocide Research*, *Holocaust and Genocide Studies*, *Genocide Studies and Prevention*) offers any articles with

⁵⁹ Naomi Adelson, “The Embodiment of Inequity: Health Disparities in Aboriginal Canada,” *Canadian Journal of Public Health* 96, no. 2 (2005): S45–61.

⁶⁰ Stephen W. Smith, “CAR’s History: The Past of a Tense Present,” in *Making Sense of the Central African Republic*, ed. Tatiana Carayannis and Louisa Lombard (London: Zed, 2015), 18, 20–3.

⁶¹ Dennis D. Cordell, “Des ‘réfugiés’ dans l’Afrique précoloniale?: L’exemple de la Centrafrique, 1850–1910,” trans. Marc-Antoine Pérouse De Montclos, *Politique africaine* 85, no. 1 (2002): 22–3; Smith, “CAR’s History,” 18–19.

⁶² *Ibid.*, 24–5.

⁶³ *Ibid.*, 22, 26.

Figure 2 Annual conflict fatalities in the Central African Republic based on UCDP and ACLED data.¹²²

sustained research on CAR which occurs only as a datapoint in datasets.⁶⁴ Even though it usually ranks highly for mass violence risk,⁶⁵ the fatalities in the last decades have never surged above the low thousands (see Figure 2) – violence not extensive enough to warrant in-depth atrocity research. Furthermore, the agents of violence organize themselves in ever-changing alliances and lack uniform targets. Militia organize themselves fluidly in “networks that can be activated when the need arises,” following the “long tradition of self-defence groups” in CAR.⁶⁶ Consequently, perpetrator and victim group identities are changeable, depending on political, economic, religious, and ethnic circumstances. The systematic patterns of violence for which the genocide or atrocity concepts call are thus difficult to establish.

Undoubtedly, some forms of violent victimization in CAR can be categorized according to the protected groups in typical genocide definitions. Perhaps the clearest social divide in CAR is religious. The Christian majority constitutes about eighty-nine per cent of the population and the Muslim minority nine per cent, concentrated in the east of CAR.⁶⁷ Peaks of violence in 2013 and 2014, leading to about 200,000 internally displaced persons and similar numbers of especially Muslim refugees fleeing across the border,⁶⁸

⁶⁴ Butcher et al., “Targeted Mass Killing Data.”

⁶⁵ “Countries at Risk for Mass Killing 2022–23: Early Warning Project Statistical Risk Assessment Results,” Early Warning Project, <https://earlywarningproject.ushmm.org/reports/countries-at-risk-for-mass-killing-2022-23-early-warning-project-statistical-risk-assessment-results> (accessed 23 October 2023); “Central African Republic Country Report 2022,” Genocide Watch, <https://www.genocidewatch.com/single-post/the-central-african-republic-country-report-2022> (accessed 23 October 2023).

⁶⁶ Tatiana Carayannis and Louisa Lombard, “Making Sense of CAR: An Introduction,” in *Making Sense of the Central African Republic*, ed. Tatiana Carayannis and Louisa Lombard (London: Zed, 2015), 7.

⁶⁷ “Central African Republic,” CIA: The World Factbook, <https://www.cia.gov/the-world-factbook/countries/central-african-republic/#people-and-society> (accessed 29 August 2023).

⁶⁸ Matthew Coldiron et al., “Retrospective Mortality among Refugees from the Central African Republic Arriving in Chad, 2014,” *Conflict and Health* 11, no. 1 (2017): 2.

coincided with clashes between predominantly Christian militia (so-called *anti-balaka*) and predominantly Muslim militia (so-called *Séléka*) (see Figure 2). Although the grievances voiced by the Christian militia are claimed to be of political nature,⁶⁹ the importance of religion as a factor of violence should not be understated. A study of dominantly Muslim refugees in Chad in the wake of this violence found that 89.5 per cent of deaths reported by refugee households were due to violence.⁷⁰ Ethnic favouritism in politics has increased since the late 1980s⁷¹ and victimization and perpetration based on ethnicity also occur. When alliances in a former *Séléka* sub-militia broke down in 2020 in northeast CAR, the intra-group violence followed ethnic faultlines.⁷²

However, as the political elites in CAR point out, ethnicity does not determine political association or economic class and elites are critical of ethnic favouritism in political processes.⁷³ Political and economic factors are often crucial factors in the immense factionalism seen in CAR. In 2018, the disbanded *Séléka*, which re-emerged as the so-called “ex-*Séléka*,” comprised eight main sub-groups (that in turn can be further sub-divided). Alliances within these sub-groups are constantly shifting, and political and economic factors are integral to any sub-group’s expansionist agenda targeted at fellow ex-*Séléka* sub-groups or others.⁷⁴ In turn, the anti-balaka, “formed mainly in the mid-2000s to fight road bandits (*zaraguinas*) and armed pastoralists”⁷⁵ are yet more difficult to aggregate into a proper group, since they are comprised of often very localized armed groups and criminal gangs.⁷⁶ While the anti-balaka, when taken as a whole, was the single most dangerous armed group for humanitarian operations, perpetrating thirty-seven per cent of incidents, almost half (forty-eight per cent) of incidents of violence against humanitarian workers were committed by unidentified assailants.⁷⁷ More recently a new rebel alliance has formed against the government, the so-called *Coalition des patriotes pour le changement* (CPC), whose composition of some former *Séléka* groups (e.g. UPC, MPC) but also their former *anti-balaka* enemies and former president Bozizé, formerly the main target of *Séléka* activities in 2013, exemplifies the complexities of factionalism in CAR.⁷⁸

Furthermore, violence in CAR is diverse, opportunistic, and often highly disaggregated. While a 2011 study into human rights abuses found that just over half of all reported incidents of “killing, intentional injury, sexual abuse, rape, abduction, and forced recruitment” was perpetrated by armed groups (i.e. militias but also criminal gangs and highwaymen), the other half of violent incidents were in fact perpetrated by individuals.⁷⁹ A focus on

⁶⁹ Carayannis and Lombard, “An Introduction,” 8.

⁷⁰ Coldiron et al., “Retrospective Mortality,” 3–5.

⁷¹ Louisa Lombard, *State of Rebellion: Violence and Intervention in the Central African Republic* (London: NBN International, 2016), 120–1.

⁷² Tim Glawion and Anne-Clémence Le Noan, “Rebel Governance or Governance in Rebel Territory? Extraction and Services in Ndélé, Central African Republic,” *Small Wars & Insurgencies* 34, no. 1 (2023): 39–42.

⁷³ Laurence Wohlers, “A Central African Elite Perspective on the Struggles of the Central African Republic,” in *Making Sense of the Central African Republic*, ed. Tatiana Carayannis and Louisa Lombard (London: Zed, 2015), 299–300.

⁷⁴ Peer Schouten and Fiona Southward, “Central African Republic: A Conflict Mapping” (Antwerp: International Peace Information Service, 2018), 17–28; Glawion and Le Noan, “Rebel Governance?” 41–2.

⁷⁵ Schouten and Southward, “A Conflict Mapping,” 28.

⁷⁶ *Ibid.*, 28–37.

⁷⁷ *Ibid.*, 28–37.

⁷⁸ “CPC,” Uppsala Conflict Data Program, <https://ucdp.uu.se/actor/7870>, (accessed 27 July 2024).

⁷⁹ Alina Potts, Kathleen Myer, and Les Roberts, “Measuring Human Rights Violations in a Conflict-Affected Country: Results from a Nationwide Cluster Survey in Central African Republic,” *Conflict and Health* 5, no. 1 (2011): 11.

organized mass violence from the perspective of atrocity frameworks thus would not capture about half of the incidents of direct violence in CAR. Indeed, rape was the most reported form of violence in the study and three-quarters of the perpetrators were not armed groups but individuals.⁸⁰

Insecurity, violence, and deprivation in CAR are among the most extreme in the world and studying their entwinement is crucial from a capability perspective. The Central African Institute of Statistics records that between 2018 and 2019 only fourteen per cent of the population had access to electricity, only fifty-nine per cent had access to proper drinking water, almost twenty-four per cent of the population was married before the age of fifteen, and the female literacy rate for the ages of fifteen to twenty-four was thirty per cent (more recent data are not offered).⁸¹ Life expectancy in CAR, according to the WHO, is at fifty-three years, more than twenty years below the world average and, although it has been rising, is projected to substantially lag behind developments of nearly all nations.⁸² An assessment from 2023 found that underreporting of birth and death rates in UN recording and modelling of mortality in CAR masks “approximately 100,000 deaths per year” which amounts to the highest annual nationwide mortality in the world in 2009–23 since the Rwandan genocide and civil war in 1994.⁸³ This is an annual human toll comparable to all combined fatalities during the Bosnian civil war and genocide (104,732 victims) over its entire three-year period that features centrally in atrocity and conflict research.⁸⁴ While yearly fatalities due to violence in CAR show several peaks (see Figure 2), mortality from overall deprivation has remained exceedingly high, far outstripping, but often directly related to, the deaths from direct violence. Diseases constitute the main direct cause of mortality, but the serious levels of food deprivation in the population substantially increase their susceptibility to them.⁸⁵ The 2023 mortality study further stresses that it “cannot distinguish the relative importance of decades of ongoing conflict, extreme poverty, the economic disruptions since 2020, or the widespread disruption efforts of the Wagner Group [or other violent groups, see Figure 3] in causing the extreme mortality.”⁸⁶ Analysing longer-term relationships between violence, deprivation, and health at the country level, I find statistically significant moderate or strong correlations between violent deaths and undernourishment, based on Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) data,

⁸⁰ Ibid.

⁸¹ “Institut Centrafricain des Statistiques et des Etudes Economiques et Sociales,” ICASEES, <https://icasees.org/index.php/> (accessed 26 July 2023).

⁸² “Central African Republic Data,” WHO, 2019, <https://data.who.int/countries/140> (accessed 27 July 2024); for projections: Kyle J. Foreman et al., “Forecasting Life Expectancy, Years of Life Lost, and All-Cause and Cause-Specific Mortality for 250 Causes of Death: Reference and Alternative Scenarios for 2016–40 for 195 Countries and Territories,” *The Lancet* 392, no. 10159 (2018): 2052–90.

⁸³ Karume Gang et al., “Cross-Sectional Survey in Central African Republic Finds Mortality 4-Times Higher than UN Statistics: How Can We Not Know the Central African Republic is in Such an Acute Humanitarian Crisis?” *Conflict and Health* 17, no. 1 (2023); Les Roberts and Jennifer O’Keefe, “Two Months after ‘Cross-sectional Survey in Central African Republic Finds Mortality 4-times Higher than UN Statistics’ Was Published, Wondering Why the World Does Not Care,” *Research Communities* (blog), 28 June 2023, <https://sustainabilitycommunity.springernature.com/posts/two-months-after-cross-sectional-survey-in-central-african-republic-finds-mortality-4-times-higher-than-un-statistics-was-published-wondering-why-the-world-does-not-care>.

⁸⁴ Ewa Tabeau and Jan Zwierchowski, “A Review of Estimation Methods for Victims of the Bosnian War and the Khmer Rouge Regime,” in *Counting Civilian Casualties: An Introduction to Recording and Estimating Nonmilitary Deaths in Conflict*, ed. Taylor B. Seybolt, Jay D. Aronson, and Baruch Fischhoff (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2013), 220.

⁸⁵ Gang et al., “Mortality 4-Times Higher in CAR.”

⁸⁶ Ibid., 8.

Figure 3 Heatmap of annual conflict fatality data in the Central African Republic disaggregated by actor dyads. Darker squares indicate more fatalities per actor dyad per year. Numbers displayed in squares are fatalities per actor dyad per year.

numbers of internally displaced persons, based on United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) data, and real GDP, based on International Monetary Fund (IMF) data (see Table 1).⁸⁷ Deprivation and lack of access to health facilities caused by displacement, in turn, is associated with increased susceptibility to and lethality of diseases, including non-communicable ones,⁸⁸ and undernourishment, which frequently causes a severely weakened immune system response to diseases.⁸⁹

⁸⁷ "Central African Republic – FAOSTAT," Food and Agriculture Organization of the UN, 2023, <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#country/37> (accessed 27 June 2024); "Real GDP Growth," IMF, 2023, https://www.imf.org/external/datamapper/NGDP_RPCH@WEO (accessed 27 June 2024); "Refugee Statistics," UNHCR, <https://www.unhcr.org/refugee-statistics/> (accessed 22 October 2023). A study on weather impacts on food security in CAR found that "food insecurity was rather linked to violent conflicts than to a climatic shock." Markus Enenkel et al., "Food Security Monitoring via Mobile Data Collection and Remote Sensing: Results from the Central African Republic," ed. Hany A. El-Shemy, *PLOS ONE* 10, no. 11 (2015): 7.

⁸⁸ Israel Oluwaseyidayo Idris et al., "Factors Influencing Severity of Recurrent Malaria in a Conflict-Affected State of South Sudan: An Unmatched Case-Control Study," *Conflict and Health* 16, no. 1 (2022): 34.

⁸⁹ Sébastien Breurec et al., "Etiology and Epidemiology of Diarrhea in Hospitalized Children from Low Income Country: A Matched Case-Control Study in Central African Republic," ed. Edward T. Ryan, *PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases* 10, no. 1 (2016).

Table 1 Correlations between conflict fatalities, displaced persons and refugees, real GDP, and undernourishment in the Central African Republic.

	ACLED	UCDP	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.
1. Real GDP growth	-0.447** [-0.71, -0.07]	-0.553*** [-0.76, -0.25]	1				
2. IDPs	0.695*** [0.42, 0.85]	0.681*** [0.44, 0.83]	-0.3497** [-0.61, -0.03]	1			
3. Refugees	0.52* [0.17, 0.76]	0.449* [0.12, 0.69]	-0.00619 [-0.33, 0.32]	0.879*** [0.78, 0.94]	1		
4. IDPs + refugees	0.637*** [0.33, 0.82]	0.59*** [0.3, 0.78]	-0.1919 [-0.49, 0.14]	-	-	1	
5. Undernourishment	0.805*** [0.57, 0.92]	0.779*** [0.52, 0.91]	-0.462** [-0.74, -0.04]	0.726*** [0.43, 0.88]	0.724*** [0.43, 0.88]	0.734*** [0.44, 0.89]	1

Notes: All data at country level. * $p < 0.10$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$. 95% confidence intervals in square brackets. Variables and data: ACLED (1997–2023) “fatalities”; UCPD (1991–2022) “best_est” and missing values between 1993 and 1999 filled with 0; 1. IMF (1980–2022) real GDP annual % change; 2. FAO 3-year average of % of undernourished persons (2000–2022); 3. UNHCR (1986–2022) refugees and internally displaced persons (IDPs). For comparisons to FAO, 3-year averages for the respective data were calculated. All correlations are limited by the time period of whichever variable’s timespan is shortest.

While it is unsurprising that violence and deprivation over the last decades are correlated, the fundamental problem of violence, deprivation, and mortality in CAR reaches deeper. CAR has seen continually high levels of violence during the nineteenth-century slave drives, colonial forced labour for concessionary and non-concessionary resource extraction,⁹⁰ occasional flare-ups of violence during Bokassa’s reign, and high, sustained levels of violence since 2009.⁹¹ The high lethality of persisting violence over the preceding fifteen years is thus amplified by such earlier violence and deprivation that have kept CAR at a low baseline of health and economic development. In turn, such longstanding structural economic and political deprivations have been crucial determinants of further deprivation and violence. State employment is ultimately the sole guarantor of salary and privilege, yet as of 2014 only one in about 150 people in CAR had a state job and stable and lucrative other employment forms are exceedingly scarce.⁹² State officials and companies – often parastatal, run by foreigners or by Muslims (themselves often conflated with “foreigners”) – use their positions for short-term self-enrichment.⁹³ Rebel strongholds may tolerate provisions of some services by the government or humanitarian organizations in their territory, but can turn rapidly against civilians at signs of conflict.⁹⁴ Hence, sixty-nine per cent of reported violent incidents between 2012 and 2017 predominantly targeted civilians.⁹⁵

⁹⁰ Smith, “CAR’s History,” 19–23.

⁹¹ Lombard, *State of Rebellion*, 121.

⁹² *Ibid.*, 122.

⁹³ Roland Marchal, “Being Rich, Being Poor: Wealth and Fear in the Central African Republic,” in *Making Sense of the Central African Republic*, ed. Tatiana Carayannis and Louisa Lombard (London: Zed, 2015), 53–75; Stephen W. Smith, “The Elite’s Road to Riches in a Poor Country,” in *Making Sense of the Central African Republic*, ed. Tatiana Carayannis and Louisa Lombard (London: Zed, 2015), 102–22.

⁹⁴ Glawion and Le Noan, “Rebel Governance?”

⁹⁵ Schouten and Southward, “A Conflict Mapping,” 13.

CAR state forces cannot control the borders and fluid movements of armed actors from across the borders to Chad, Sudan, and South Sudan – themselves highly volatile and deprived states – are frequent sources of conflict.⁹⁶ In 2018 CAR's army had 7,700 registered forces,⁹⁷ wholly insufficient to patrol the borders of a country twice the size of Italy and located in arguably the most deprived and violent region of the world. Before the millennium, armed movements from civil wars and atrocities in Chad and Darfur found asylum in CAR and led to increased militarization of pastoralists and others.⁹⁸ In 2009, members from the Lord's Resistance Army (a rebel group from northern Uganda) on the backfoot from Ugandan army advances fled to CAR and pursued destruction there, inhibited only by Ugandan forces stationed in southeast CAR (until 2017) with US support.⁹⁹ Even within the country, the state has little control. In 2017, 339 roadblocks were identified in CAR with forty-one per cent operated by government forces, fifty-three per cent by former *Séléka*, and fourteen per cent by *anti-balaka* (some roadblocks are operated by multiple groups, hence the added percentages are greater than 100 per cent).¹⁰⁰ Furthermore, road bandits, looking back on centuries of practice, control about seventy per cent of the country's road network with major detrimental effects for local populations but elicit barely any international concern or response because of their localized and disaggregate nature.¹⁰¹ Only "the most highly valued goods" circulate beyond the local levels, leading to "radical price disparities for basic foodstuffs between nearby places."¹⁰² State resources to exercise monopolies of violence on local levels are severely limited. The prefecture Haut-Mbomou (with the regional capital Obo), for example, has "one sole police officer for the entire prefecture" across an area approximately the size of Croatia.¹⁰³ No mail is delivered beyond the borders of the capital,¹⁰⁴ and high-level officials have no means of regularly contacting local authorities.¹⁰⁵

Economics, health, and organized violence are interconnected and the overall state of deprivation has been sustained over such a long time that it cannot be considered the outcome of one particular violent regime. Since 2006, CAR has always had substantial numbers of internally displaced persons, with a minimum of 51,679 in 2012, a maximum of 894,421 in 2013, and an average of 408,089 (and median 411,785). FAO data reaching back to 2000 record perennially high levels of undernourishment affecting more than thirty per cent of the population with sharply rising recent trends that approach the fifty per cent mark.¹⁰⁶ Economic deprivation and political disenfranchisement are significant contributors to violence. The *Séléka* cited general

⁹⁶ Glawion Tim, *The Security Arena in Africa: Local Order-Making in the Central African Republic, Somaliland, and South Sudan* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2020), 6–11.

⁹⁷ Schouten and Southward, "A Conflict Mapping," 15.

⁹⁸ Roland Marchal, "CAR and the Regional (Dis)Order," in *Making Sense of the Central African Republic*, ed. Tatiana Carayannis and Louisa Lombard (London: Zed, 2015), 176–7.

⁹⁹ Ledio Cakaj, "In Unclaimed Land: The Lord's Resistance Army in CAR," in *Making Sense of the Central African Republic*, ed. Tatiana Carayannis and Louisa Lombard (London: Zed, 2015), 267–94.

¹⁰⁰ Peer Schouten, *Roadblock Politics: The Origins of Violence in Central Africa* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2022), 184.

¹⁰¹ *Ibid.*, 180; Lombard, *State of Rebellion*, 127.

¹⁰² Schouten, *Roadblock Politics*, 179.

¹⁰³ Tim, *The Security Arena in Africa*, 79.

¹⁰⁴ Lombard, *State of Rebellion*, 98.

¹⁰⁵ Schouten, *Roadblock Politics*, 93.

¹⁰⁶ "FAO."

patterns of Muslim and northeastern marginalization for their violent advance.¹⁰⁷ *Anti-balaka* often express dismay over the foreign or Muslim-run economy. Both groups (and their successors and sub-groups) recruit substantial numbers of unemployed and disenfranchised youth.¹⁰⁸ Rebels' governance activities are often limited to a mere extraction of economic benefits and future territorial aggressions are considered in light of potential economic gains.¹⁰⁹ Militia and armed groups also curate their politics, violence, and goals to gain rebel status that in turn makes them eligible for economically attractive Disarmament, Demobilization, and Reintegration programmes, run by the government and international organizations.¹¹⁰ The primary economic motivation for the violence of all roadblock groups is apparent. Roadblocks constitute a main source of income for the larger armed groups, and anecdotal evidence confirms that small-scale, localized highway-men seek to escape economic and political entrapment.¹¹¹

While economic deprivation is thus a clear motivation for violence in CAR, less is known about the reverse direction, the degree to which violence leads to measurable economic deprivation. Undoubtedly, constantly factionalized violence, short-term extractive behaviour of violent groups, political agents, and companies, high price disparities between localities, and high costs of transporting any good across CAR's intensely levied and barely developed infrastructure are not to the greater economic or medical welfare of CAR's population.¹¹² Broad correlations at the national level are indicative. During peak violence between 2013 and 2015, CAR recorded its most precipitous economic decline (by over thirty-six per cent in real GDP) since the beginning of recording by the IMF in 1980, and violent deaths and real GDP are statistically significantly correlated (see Table 1). Similarly, whereas on the global level causal relationships between conflict and food insecurity are well-researched,¹¹³ and, as shown in Table 1, violence and food insecurity exhibit the strongest correlations together with IDPs (themselves likely caused by violence), the causal directions and degrees of these interrelations in CAR are in much more need of further investigation. Almost nothing is known about health as a motivator for violence specifically in CAR, although increased health and life expectancy have been associated with lower levels of conflict in countries.¹¹⁴ Conversely, causal links between violence and overall poor population health – in the form of food insecurity and susceptibility to infection by and negative outcomes of diseases – are undeniable in general, but are more difficult to measure in their specifics, not least since economic deprivation, itself partially caused by and partially causing violence, is also intricately related to poor health. A 2023 comprehensive survey of health facilities across CAR found that almost half were completely or partially destroyed, citing longer-term disrepair and destruction or raiding during the conflict as the two principal reasons.¹¹⁵ Another

¹⁰⁷ Louisa Lombard, *Hunting Game: Raiding Politics in the Central African Republic* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2020), 192–5.

¹⁰⁸ Schouten and Southward, "A Conflict Mapping," 31–3; Lombard, *State of Rebellion*, 129, 177.

¹⁰⁹ Glawion and Le Noan, "Rebel Governance?"; Schouten and Southward, "A Conflict Mapping," 41–96.

¹¹⁰ Lombard, *State of Rebellion*, 127–40.

¹¹¹ *Ibid.*, 127, 135.

¹¹² Schouten, *Roadblock Politics*, 146–201.

¹¹³ Charles Martin-Shields and Wolfgang Stojetz, "Food Security and Conflict: Empirical Challenges and Future Opportunities for Research and Policy Making on Food Security and Conflict," *World Development* 119 (2019): 150–64.

¹¹⁴ Tyler Kustra, "HIV/AIDS, Life Expectancy, and the Opportunity Cost Model of Civil War," *Journal of Conflict Resolution* 61, no. 10 (2017): 2130–57.

¹¹⁵ "HeRAMS République centrafricaine : Rapport de référence 2023" (Organisation mondiale de la Santé, 2023), 8.

study from 2010 estimates that over half its surveyed respondents had inadequate access to health facilities and met criteria for depression and anxiety from experiencing or witnessing violence.¹¹⁶ The capability approach calls for an integrated study of these different, often endogenous, deprivations, rather than making violence the sole dependent variable of interest.

The nexus between health, precarity, and violence deserves much more attention even beyond CAR. Much merit lies in studying them together as capability deprivation. The capability perspective, firstly, significantly increases our purview and includes cases, such as CAR, examined here, but also many of its neighbouring sub-Saharan nations, that do not fall under the narrower remit of mass violence scholarship. Secondly, the capability approach explicitly calls for examining the multi-causal relations of violence to deprivation and excess mortality with figures that can ultimately far exceed (as in CAR) deaths from direct violence alone that dominate the considerations of not only atrocity but also conflict scholarship more generally. If we care – as recent scholars emphasize in their re-assessments of the normative framework underlying mass violence concepts¹¹⁷ – about “innocent” noncombatant deaths dying as a direct or indirect consequence of continual violence, we must increase our purview and take into account the more “indirect” victims of violence.

Conclusions, Limitations, and Consequences

Atrocity research can significantly broaden its causal and spatio-temporal scope when considering capability deprivations as part of its field. Health and food insecurity especially, and humankind’s role in creating or preventing them, should constitute a more integral part of such research. The capability approach offers four crucial advantages:

(1) *Explicit normative granularity and observable structures*: The capability approach focuses on observable behaviours and patterns, rather than intentions and motivations that can only be inferred. Its general thrust is away from an overreliance on perpetrator motivations that ultimately have to be individualizable to qualify as deliberate or genocidal killing and explicitly considers the norms underpinning socio-political, cultural, and economic structures of violence and deprivation. It thereby avoids ignoring violence and deprivations that fall under an effectively arbitrary threshold of destruction and enables fine-grained considerations of different patterns of deprivation. Its focus on observable deprivation rather than intention, often inferred from *ex post* analysis, makes it particularly useful for guiding long-term and acute preventative measures. While all approaches to violence are ultimately driven by a normative commitment to the victims, the capability framework serves this commitment much more fully by considering the different forms of loss of lives and suffering comprehensively.

(2) *Multi-causality of violence and deprivation*: The capability approach considers a broader range of violence impacts and deprivation, including those less visible and

¹¹⁶ Patrick Vinck and Phuong Pham, “Association of Exposure to Violence and Potential Traumatic Events with Self-Reported Physical and Mental Health Status in the Central African Republic,” *JAMA* 304, no. 5 (2010): 544–52.

¹¹⁷ Moses, *Problems of Genocide*, 18–19; Alexander, “The Ethics of Violence,” 246–7.

sometimes accepted near-fatalistically (famines or diseases). While capability deprivation has many sources, including substantial natural ones (say, earthquakes), its framework moves decidedly away from naturalizations or biologizations. Furthermore, because the direct violence of atrocities effectively always begins in earlier forms of deprivation, enduring at a lower intensity and perhaps less expansively so, the capability approach inherently includes these in its purview. Some quantitative models implicitly acknowledge the importance of such deprivations to atrocity when they consider various deprivations (e.g. high infant mortality)¹¹⁸ to predict atrocity or conflict onset. Nonetheless, since atrocity or conflict are the dependent variables, such modelling prioritizes mass killings and instrumentalizes other forms of deprivation, like structurally high mortality, even if those deprivations often ultimately claim more victims than the dependent variable itself. Since violence and other forms of deprivation (e.g. economic, nutritional, health-related) are often highly endogenous or reversely causal,¹¹⁹ holistic considerations of loss of lives that look at changeable interrelations of different deprivations, rather than designating direct violence as the singular variable of interest, is not only ethically necessary but methodologically sound.

(3) *Non-arbitrary spatio-temporal windows of consideration*: The capability approach includes the short-term and very explosive forms of violence seen in atrocities, but also considers long-term forms of deprivation. The capability approach is explicit about paying attention to the ways and underlying norms in which we slice our spatio-temporal horizons of consideration.

(4) *Abatement of deprivation and policy*: Although not elaborated here, the capability approach's structural perspective inherently demands a continued focus on deprivation where deprivation exists, even when, say, the particularly genocidal episode is over but has (un-)intended consequences of expansive, long-term deprivation of populations. The capability approach also seeks structural rather than interventionist solutions to mass deprivation. Specific policy recommendations concerning mortality reduction include the need for a global epidemiological institution for real-time mortality surveillance particularly in neglected regions with little data¹²⁰ and increased preventative focus in conflict-vulnerable countries on communicable diseases that overwhelmingly drive indirect conflict-mortality.¹²¹

Thus, the capability approach enabled, indeed ethically demanded, our consideration of victims of colonialism who did not have the "privilege" of being violently killed in a genocide, narrowly defined, but died of colonizer-imposed capability deprivation by being forcibly displaced, exposed to diseases, and deprived of livelihoods and nutrition. Similarly, the capability approach called for a holistic investigation of extreme mortality in CAR. This approach not only offers a more comprehensive view of the types of suffering and death, including man-made environments that increase exposure to diseases, but also multi-directional causes of such suffering. Colonial

¹¹⁸ Ulfelder and Valentino, "Assessing Risks of State-Sponsored Mass Killing."

¹¹⁹ Martin-Shields and Stojetz, "Food Security and Conflict," 152–9.

¹²⁰ Francesco Checchi and Les Roberts, "Documenting Mortality in Crises: What Keeps us from Doing Better?" *PLOS Medicine* 5, no. 7 (2008).

¹²¹ Jawad et al., "Estimating Indirect Mortality," 6.

¹²² Data: Clionadh Raleigh et al., "Introducing ACLED: An Armed Conflict Location and Event Dataset," *Journal of Peace Research* 47, no. 5 (2010): 651–60; Ralph Sundberg, Kristine Eck, and Joakim Kreutz, "Introducing the UCDP Non-State Conflict Dataset," *Journal of Peace Research* 49, no. 2 (2012): 351–62.

violence and deprivation still largely conform to the sustained asymmetry between perpetrator (colonizer) and victim groups (indigenous populations) expected by atrocity research (even if at certain points in time and space, e.g. during early European colonial settlements, these group categories may have occasionally been less stable). This asymmetry perhaps partially explains why scholarship here has advanced furthest in the direction of the capability approach. However, the case of CAR showed that the capability approach does not presuppose stable orderings between perpetrator and victim groups and, furthermore, explicitly demands examining changing interrelations between violence and other forms of deprivation. In CAR, violence drives and is driven by economic deprivation, political disenfranchisement, displacement, and poor health, while likely causing the severe food insecurities leading to yet worsened population health.

Nonetheless, there are limitations to the capability approach for atrocity research. Probably the biggest concern of atrocity scholars would be that the capability approach is simply too broad. The capability approach seems to level what genocide and atrocity scholars have assiduously been attempting to characterize as a *categorically different* form of violence that is (typically) understood as highly asymmetric and driven by very agentive (and ideological) actors, rather than broader and longer-term violence and its interaction with socio-political, economic, and health deprivation. This limitation is ultimately inherent in the capability approach as such and, I believe, is simply part of the risk of the approach's holistic framework that calls for the consideration of the less direct victims of violence, due to excess mortality caused by interrelations between conflict, malnutrition, disease, and economic and political deprivation.

Despite these shortcomings, I have attempted to show how the capability approach integrates well into recent developments in atrocity scholarship that questions some of its foundational normative assumptions and the conventional patterns of scrutiny of such violence (ideology-driven agents with clear intent and blueprints to kill within very constrained causal and spatio-temporal horizons). What the capability approach contributes to these developments is a further move away from the narrow focus on direct violence towards a significantly much more complete picture of destruction and deprivation. Indeed, the move away from direct violence towards a widened focus on violence and deprivation as a broader causal driver of excess mortality has already been anticipated by recent research on the depopulation of indigenous peoples under European colonialism, especially in relation to disease.

On the other hand, as I have tried to show more extensively in the case of CAR, the approach also opens up largely ignored cases of low-intensity, long-term states of violence and its interaction with food insecurity and low health, amplified by CAR's low development baseline. While organized direct violence in CAR is certainly substantial (more than 17,000 victims are recorded in ACLED and UCDP since 2000), it is not "enough" to be an integral part of atrocity scholarship. Yet, the multi-directional causal relations between violence, lack of healthcare, food insecurity, and economic deprivation in CAR could hardly have more severe consequences for mortality. If 100,000 Central Africans per year can vanish between the cracks of insufficient statistical mortality records by the UN without anyone's notice, save from specialists, atrocity scholars must question their normative and analytical categories, given the considerable role of violence in CAR's extreme mortality and deprivation.

If saving lives underwrites the ethical imperative of researching atrocities and conflicts, the holistic perspective of the capability approach is more explicit and expansive in its consideration of violence's victims. It follows through on these normative assumptions that predicate research of violence and demands a much more extensive investigation into the causes and consequences of violence.

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